

Selective Ion Exchange Removal of Chromate from Phosphate, Sulphate, Chloride and Chromate Bearing Effluents

G. SAHA* and G. S. BHATTACHARYYA

Central Water Quality Control Cell, Hindustan Fertilizer Corporation Ltd., Durgapur-713 212

and

N. KURMAIH

R. E. College, Durgapur-713 209

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Preferential exchange and elution of chromate over phosphate and sulphate on strong base anion exchanger has been investigated following the technique of frontal analysis, and operating conditions have been optimized for the desired separation. Hydrodynamic aspect have been studied qualitatively. An indigenously available strong base resin Deacidite FF-1P could effectively be used in the technique as the stationary phase.

HESLER and Oberhofer¹ removed chromate selectively from cooling tower blow down water on chloride form of the strong base anion exchanger, Dowex-1. Chromate, phosphate, sulphate and chloride are the anions present in appreciable quantities in cooling water under conventional dianodic treatment. It has been found by the present study that Cl^- ions have practically very little effect on the selective removal of chromate on chloride form of strong base anion exchanger. So the process concerned is actually selective removal of chromate from phosphate and sulphate. In this study chromate was removed selectively, following the principle of frontal analysis², from a synthetic solution of CrO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} and SO_4^{2-} on chloride form of Deacidite FF-1P (a product of M/s. Ion Exchange India Ltd.). Due to higher affinity of the exchanger for chromate ions together with conversion of the exchanger at low pH from chromate to dichromate and polychromate forms, the exchanged sulphate and phosphate ions almost get fully replaced by chromate ions. At break-through point almost whole of the resin bed gets converted into dichromate form and very little into sulphate and phosphate forms. Elution with high pH NaCl solution of the dichromate form of resin results in a concentrated chromate solution having minor contamination of sulphate and phosphate.

Experimental

Strong base anion exchanger of size -16+52 mesh, density 3.5 g/ml, % swelling 185, strong base capacity 1.22 meq/ml was used for all experiments in suitable glass column. Before use, the resins were conditioned by repeatedly washing with sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid solutions. Chromate-phosphate-sulphate synthetic solution was

prepared from analytical grade potassium chromate, sodium sulphate and potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate. Composition of the synthetic solution was maintained as K_2CrO_4 : 100 mg/l as CrO_4 , Na_2SO_4 : 800 mg/l as SO_4 and KH_2PO_4 : 100 mg/l as PO_4 ; the composition representing the proportion of CrO_4^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} in typical cooling water. The synthetic solution (exhaustant) was passed through chloride form of the resin bed in the down flow direction and after breakthrough (5% leakage) the bed was regenerated first with a mixed solution of 10% NaCl+5% NaOH and finally with only 10% NaCl. First fraction was collected upto caustic breakthrough and after changing the regenerant to only 10% NaCl, the final fraction was collected from caustic breakthrough to visual disappearance of chromate colour in a 5 mm glass tube. The fractions were then analysed for Na_2CrO_4 , NaOH, NaCl and combined ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{Na}_2\text{PO}_4$); Na_2CrO_4 , NaOH and NaCl were estimated volumetrically. To save time ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{Na}_2\text{PO}_4$) value was estimated by subtracting from total dissolved solid the combined value of Na_2CrO_4 , NaOH and NaCl. Colorimetric estimation of SO_4 and PO_4 in the fraction confirmed the validity of above procedure. The regeneration rate was maintained at 0.2 gpm/cft. Results of successful experiments pertain to resin bed of 40 cm high and 3 cm diam.

Results and Discussion

With the stated experimental procedure, studies were performed to see (a) the effect of column diameter on chromate exchange capacity and selective chromate exchange, (b) the effect of feed pH on chromate exchange capacity, selectivity and

recovery and (c) effect of service flow rate on chromate exchange capacity. Results have been shown in Figs. 1-6.

As can be seen from Fig. 1, the chromate exchange capacity of strong base anion exchanger increased linearly with increasing column diameter up to 3.0 cm diam. This is due to the fact that

Fig. 1. Dependence of chromate exchange capacity on column diameter.

hydrodynamic aspects^a play an important role during chromate exchange and to minimize the effect, resin bed of proper diameter should be chosen. The effect has been depicted in Figs. 2 and 3 where elution history during regeneration have been plotted with 10 and 30 mm diam resin beds. With 10 mm diam there is complete diffusion of Na_2CrO_4 and $(\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{Na}_3\text{PO}_4)$ bands whereas with 30 mm diam resin bed, the said diffusion is negligible, indicating almost complete separation. Further experiments indicated that resin bed of minimum 30 mm diam with minimum aspect ratio (diam : length) of 1 : 3 are optimum for desired separation.

Fig. 2. Elution history during regeneration with 100 mm high and 10 mm diam resin bed.

Fig. 3. Elution history during regeneration with 400 mm high and 30 mm diam resin bed.

The hydrodynamic aspects, specially fingering^a, were also observed during regeneration leading to decreased chromate concentration and increased regenerant concentration in the effluent. The effect could be eliminated by thoroughly back washing the resin bed before service and gradually attaining the regeneration rate of 0.2 gpm/cft.

Fig. 4 indicates that chromate exchange capacity of the resin increased with decreasing pH of the exhaustant. This is due to conversion of the exchanger into dichromate and polychromate forms at low pH.

Fig. 4. Dependence of chromate exchange capacity on pH of exhaustant at 4 gpm/cft exhaustion flow rate.

Fig. 5 shows the extent of selectivity and recovery of exchanged chromate during regeneration, as a function of pH of the exhaustant. The selectivity of the exchanger for chromate was taken, unconventionally, as the percentage of chromate over (phosphate+sulphate) in the first fraction of effluent collected during regeneration. It is seen that selectivity is maximum at pH 3.5 and decreases below pH 3.5. The recovery is maximum at pH 4.0 and decreases thereafter. The decrease of selectivity and recovery is due to the fact that at very low pH chromate gets strongly adsorbed on the exchanger resulting in a difficult elution, also a portion of the exchanged chromate gets reduced by resin structure prior to regeneration.

Fig. 6 shows a very common fact that exchange capacity increases with decreasing exhaustion flow rate.

Fig. 5. Dependence of recovery and selectivity on exhaustant pH at 4 gpm./cft. exhaustion flow rate.

Curve 'A' → Selectivity vs pH.
Curve 'B' → % Recovery vs pH.

Fig. 6. Dependence of chromate exchange capacity on exhaustion flow rate. pH of exhaustant 4.0.

As regard the effect of chloride, there is only 0.004% reduction in the chromate exchange capacity due to the presence of 200 mg/l chloride in the exhaustant.

From the aforesaid results, the optimum operating conditions at 0.2 gpm/cft regeneration rate, derived for the process are as follows: pH of the exhaustant = 4.0-4.5; flow rate of exhaustion = 2.5-3.0 gpm/cft; volume (10% NaCl + 5% NaOH) regenerant to be used = 1.5-2.0 bed volumes. Under the optimized conditions following results were obtained: exchange capacity 115-120 g CrO₄/litre resin; % recovery 94-95; composition of recovered solution (1st fraction) Na₂CrO₄ 9-10%, NaCl 2.0-2.5%, NaOH max 0.5%; (Na₂SO₄ + Na₂PO₄) 0.2-0.4%; selectivity 97-98%. Composition of the 2nd fraction was NaCl 5-8%; NaOH 3-4%; other solids 1%. The composition of the recovered solution shows that chromate has been selectively removed from phosphate and sulphate. The second fraction, after proper addition, can be used as the first regenerant for the next run in actual practice (this was not done in this experiment). The results obtained are very much appropriate for the treatment of chromate bearing cooling tower blowdown water or other similar effluents. The procedure can also be used for analytical separation of chromate from phosphate and sulphate.

References

1. J. C. HESLER and A. W. OBERHOFFER, "Mat Prot.", 1964, Vol. 3, p. 8.
2. F. HELFRICH, "Ion Exchange", McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., 1962 Edn., p. 440.
3. F. HELFRICH, "Ion Exchange", McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., 1962 Edn., p. 486.